

Research and application of plant protection techniques and implements for rice production in China

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Abstract

Rice plant protection is an essential part of the rice production. In order to achieve sustainable agricultural development and ensure national food and ecological security, there is important significance to improve the utilization of agricultural resources and enhance the control capabilities of the sudden area-wide pest infestation. Based on the review of the current status and existing problems of Rice Plant Protection Machinery (RPPM) in China, including manpower spraying equipment, small power plant protection machinery, large and medium-sized power plant protection machinery, and aviation application, the urgent needs of the new precise and efficient paddy pesticide spraying machinery in modern agricultural production were discussed. And then the future directions of RPPM were pointed out, which includes the precision spraying and efficient spraying. Finally, the countermeasures to promote the rapid development of RPPM were put forward, which including broaden the coverage of a single spraying operation, strengthening the method innovation of paddy spraying, and vigorously promote the application of aviation plant protection.

Introduction

According to a statistics, it is irreplaceable in a very long period of time that pesticides are used on crop protection for the use of pesticides can reduce the loss of grain about 15% [1]. However, Backward spraying equipment and low effective utilization of agricultural resources not only cause huge economic losses, but cause serious water and soil resources pollution, ecological system imbalance, quality decline of agricultural products as well as other human health threat problems [2].

Nowadays, there are lots of advanced spraying technologies are used in agricultural production, including automatic target sprayer[3], air-assisted low-volume sprayer[4], electrostatic spraying[5, 6], recycling sprayer[7], reduced drift sprayer[8], aero plane sprayer[9], large-scale boom sprayer[10], etc.

As for the limits of the rice-growing agricultural requirements, such as smaller row space (always less than 30cm, especially when the rice grow to the row-sealed stage, line ridge is not clear)[11, 12], poor performance of the trafficability (compared with the dry land, the flatness of paddy field mud bottom is uncontrollable, invisible, tilt, and the agricultural machinery is easier to get stuck in the mud), etc, it is difficult for the paddy field sprayer to enter into paddy field[13]. All the mentioned above technologies, therefore, have their own advantages and disadvantages in rice pesticide application.

For example, spray-boom spraying machine usually is tractor-mounted. The large-scale boom sprayer, such as GreenSeeker RT200 sprayer (Ntech Inc.), UX series sprayer (AMAZONE Inc.), 4030 series sprayer (John Deere Inc.), 3WQX air-assisted boom sprayer (Chinese Academy of Agricultural Mechanization Sciences), etc, has higher efficiency, and its working width can up to 36cm. However, along with the working width increase, there are lots of problems when the machine works in paddy field, including more total weight, more mating power, and then poorer performance of the trafficability, energy consumption and operation cost increasing [14]. Increase of working width requires larger power machine, and thus whole weight of spraying machine increases, passage performance of farm working drops, energy consumption and working cost increase; during spraying work, spray boom swings easily when traveling because of rugged farmland, and therefore it is hard to keep parallel traveling between spray boom and land surface; balance of spray boom is harder to control along with increase of spray boom length, two ends touch land surface easily which will damage machine components; moreover, along with the working width increase, longer spray booms

are needed, a litter vibration when traveling with power machine at the machine's hitch position can cause a violent swing at the end of the boom, which may cause serious damage to the spray boom[15]. According to the rice-growing agricultural requirements, its row space always less than 30cm, especially when the rice growth to the row-sealed stage, it has narrow row spacing and unclear field ridge, it is hard for spray-boom spraying machine to enter farm field to spray pesticides, the spraying functions of the boom sprayer are seriously restricted.

As a result, according to shortcomings of existing technologies, to design a special ultra-working-width precision pesticide sprayer is needed, which can broaden working scope, improve working efficiency, precisely transfer feed liquid to farm field to be sprayed, spray pesticides to crops in close range, improve working precision and reduce the losses of liquid materials such as pesticides, herbicides, foliar fertilizer, etc. [16].

Based on the review of the current status and existing problems of Rice Plant Protection Machinery (RPPM) in China, including manpower spraying equipment, small power plant protection machinery, large and medium-sized power plant protection machinery, and aviation application (spraying drones or UAVs), the urgent needs of the new precise and efficient paddy pesticide spraying machinery in modern agricultural production were discussed in this presentation. And then the future directions of RPPM were pointed out, which includes the precision spraying and efficient spraying. Finally, the countermeasures to promote the rapid development of RPPM were put forward, which including broaden the coverage of a single spraying operation, strengthening the method innovation of paddy spraying, and vigorously promote the application of aviation plant protection

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